

THE INTERPRETATION OF MOTHER IMAGE IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Zilola Ayitboyeva Babajon qizi

Teacher of Urgench Ranch University of technology

zilolahaitboyeva8@gmail.com

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Abstract. The article discusses national traditions in the expression of the image of mother in English literature. It shows the portrayal of motherhood is based on English national values, culture and traditions in the literature.

Key words: motherhood, national traditions, cultural heritage, society, nature, homeland.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются национальные традиции выражения образа матери в английской литературе. В статье показано, как изображается образ матери в английской литературе на основе национальных ценностях, культуры и традиций

Ключевые слова: материнство, национальные традиции, культурное наследие, общество, природа, родина.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz adabiyotida ona timsolini ifodalashda milliy an'analar ko'rinishi ifodalab berilgan. Maqolada ingliz adabiyotidagi ona obrazini milliy qadriyatlar, madaniyat va urf odatlar orqali qanday ochib berilishi haqida keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ona obrazi, milliy qadriyatlar, madaniy meros, jamiyat, tabiat, ona vatan.

In English literature, the mother image is often a complex and multifaceted archetype. Many works depict mothers as sources of comfort and support. This archetype emphasizes the nurturing aspects of motherhood, illustrating the bond between mother and child. Mothers are frequently portrayed as sacrificing their own desires for the well-being of their children. This theme highlights the ideal of maternal love and devotion. In some narratives, the mother figure assumes a controlling role, representing societal expectations and pressures. This can lead to tension and conflict within family dynamics. Literature often contrasts the idealized mother with the flawed human reality. Characters may grapple with the expectations of motherhood versus their actual experiences.

Some texts challenge traditional mother archetypes, exploring themes of maternal ambivalence or rebellion against societal norms, offering a more nuanced portrayal of women's roles. The interpretation of the mother image can vary significantly across different cultures and historical periods, reflecting societal values and changing gender roles. Examples of works that explore the mother image include "Frankenstein" by Mary Shelley, which examines the consequences of maternal absence, and "Beloved" by Toni Morrison, which delves into the complexities of motherhood within the context of slavery.

In "Frankenstein" by Mary Shelley, the image of motherhood is complex and multifaceted, largely defined by absence and neglect. Victor Frankenstein's mother, Caroline, represents an idealized, nurturing figure. Her death deeply impacts Victor, leaving a void in his emotional life. This absence contributes to his obsessive quest for knowledge and creation, reflecting a longing for maternal care.

The Creature symbolizes a tragic absence of motherhood. Created without a mother, he experiences profound loneliness and seeks companionship and acceptance. His rejection by

society mirrors a lack of maternal nurturing, leading to feelings of abandonment and rage. Victor's failure to take responsibility for his creation can be seen as a maternal failure. His abandonment of the Creature results in tragic consequences, highlighting the importance of nurturing in human development.

Victor's desire to transcend natural boundaries by creating life represents a rebellion against traditional maternal roles. His pursuit ultimately results in destruction rather than creation, suggesting the dangers of neglecting the nurturing aspect of motherhood. The novel raises questions about the influence of maternal care on identity and behavior. The Creature's violent tendencies stem from his lack of nurturing, emphasizing the critical role of a mother figure in shaping an individual.

In summary, "Frankenstein" presents a nuanced exploration of motherhood, emphasizing themes of absence, neglect, and the essential need for nurturing in human life.

In "Beloved" by Toni Morrison, the image of motherhood is central and deeply complex, reflecting themes of love, trauma, and sacrifice. Sethe, the protagonist, embodies the extreme sacrifices a mother makes for her children. Her decision to kill her daughter rather than allow her to be enslaved illustrates the desperation and depth of her maternal love. Sethe's experiences of slavery profoundly affect her motherhood. The trauma she endures impacts her ability to nurture, leading to emotional distance and haunting memories that shape her relationship with her surviving children. Despite the trauma, the bonds between mothers and their children are portrayed as powerful and enduring. Sethe's love for her children drives her actions and informs her identity, emphasizing the strength of maternal connections. The character of Beloved, who represents Sethe's deceased daughter, serves as a haunting reminder of loss and the unresolved pain of motherhood. Beloved's return challenges Sethe to confront her past and the consequences of her choices. The novel also reflects the broader context of African American motherhood during slavery, highlighting the systemic forces that disrupt maternal bonds. Mothers are often torn from their children, emphasizing the struggle to maintain familial ties in the face of oppression.

Throughout the novel, the theme of healing emerges as Sethe seeks to reconcile her past. The narrative explores how confronting trauma can lead to a deeper understanding of motherhood and the possibility of redemption.

Overall, "Beloved" presents a profound exploration of motherhood, showcasing its complexities amidst the backdrop of historical trauma and personal sacrifice.

In "The Joy Luck Club" by Amy Tan, the image of motherhood is explored through the intricate relationships between Chinese immigrant mothers and their American-born daughters. The mothers' traditional Chinese values often clash with their daughters' American ideals. This cultural gap highlights differing expectations around family, duty, and individuality. The mothers' stories reflect immense personal sacrifices made for their children's futures. Their struggles, often rooted in hardship, emphasize the resilience and strength inherent in motherhood. The mothers' past experiences, including war and loss, shape their identities and parenting styles. This trauma impacts their relationships with their daughters, creating layers of misunderstanding and emotional distance.

Despite the conflicts, there is a deep yearning for connection and understanding. The mothers' stories reveal their hopes and dreams for their daughters, contrasting with the daughters' struggles to reconcile these expectations with their own identities. The act of

sharing stories becomes a way for both generations to bridge the gap. Through these narratives, daughters gain insight into their mothers' lives, fostering empathy and understanding. As the daughters navigate their cultural identities, they often grapple with their mothers' influences. This journey reflects the struggle to forge their own paths while acknowledging their heritage. Overall, "The Joy Luck Club" portrays motherhood as a multifaceted experience marked by love, sacrifice, and the quest for understanding across cultural divides.

In "Great Expectations" by Charles Dickens, the image of motherhood is portrayed through various characters, each representing different aspects of maternal influence and absence. Mrs. Joe Gargery: Pip's sister and guardian embodies a harsh, demanding form of motherhood. She is more focused on discipline than nurturing, reflecting the difficulties of her own life. Her treatment of Pip highlights the complexities of familial relationships and the burdens of caregiving.

Miss Havisham: Although not a traditional mother, Miss Havisham plays a significant maternal role in Pip's life. Her eccentricity and emotional manipulation profoundly affect Pip and Estella. She represents a twisted version of motherhood, where neglect and bitterness overshadow nurturing. Pip's mother is largely absent from his life, symbolizing the void that can exist in a child's emotional world. This absence contributes to Pip's longing for love and acceptance, influencing his decisions and aspirations.

The character of Biddy offers a more nurturing, supportive maternal figure. Biddy's kindness and wisdom provide Pip with comfort and guidance, contrasting sharply with the harsher maternal figures in his life. The novel explores how social class influences maternal roles. The differing approaches to motherhood among characters highlight the impact of social status on nurturing and family dynamics. Overall, "Great Expectations" presents a nuanced exploration of motherhood, illustrating how various maternal figures shape Pip's identity and experiences.

In "A Tree Grows in Brooklyn" by Betty Smith, the image of motherhood is central to the narrative and portrayed with depth and complexity. The protagonist, Francie Nolan's mother, Katie, embodies resilience and self-sacrifice. Katie works tirelessly to provide for her family, often prioritizing her children's needs over her own. Her struggles highlight the hardships faced by working-class mothers. Katie's love for Francie and her brother, Neeley, is unwavering. She encourages their education and dreams, instilling in them the values of hard work and ambition despite their challenging circumstances. The novel explores the nuanced relationship between mothers and daughters. Francie admires Katie but also grapples with her mother's sacrifices and the expectations placed on her. This dynamic illustrates the complexities of maternal love and the impact of generational differences. The story reflects the immigrant experience in early 20th-century America. Katie's struggles as an Irish immigrant shape her identity and parenting style, emphasizing the influence of cultural background on motherhood.

The novel portrays motherhood within the context of family dynamics, highlighting the interconnectedness of love, support, and struggle among family members. The title itself symbolizes resilience and growth, paralleling Francie's journey as she learns from her mother's strength and determination. Katie's nurturing enables Francie to aspire to a better future. Overall, "A Tree Grows in Brooklyn" presents a rich and multifaceted portrayal of

motherhood, emphasizing themes of resilience, sacrifice, and the deep bonds between mothers and their children.

In "The Handmaid's Tale" by Margaret Atwood, the image of motherhood is central to the narrative, reflecting themes of control, identity, and resistance. In the dystopian society of Gilead, motherhood is strictly regulated. Women are categorized primarily by their reproductive abilities, and Handmaids are forced into motherhood against their will. This coercion highlights the dehumanization of women and the loss of autonomy. Gilead promotes an idealized vision of motherhood, emphasizing fertility and the role of women as bearers of children. However, this ideal is deeply flawed, as it strips women of their rights and reduces them to mere vessels.

Offred's memories of her daughter reflect the pain of separation and loss. The bond between them serves as a powerful motivator for her actions, emphasizing the deep emotional ties that persist despite oppressive circumstances. The narrative explores how women resist the oppressive structures of Gilead. Motherhood becomes a form of rebellion, as Offred and others find ways to assert their identities and agency, even within a repressive system. Offred's recollections of her past, including her relationship with her mother, serve as a means of retaining identity and humanity. These memories contrast sharply with her current reality, highlighting the impact of loss and trauma.

The relationships among women, particularly in the face of shared oppression, illustrate the importance of solidarity. The bonds formed among Handmaids, despite their forced roles, underscore the strength found in shared experiences of motherhood and resistance. Overall, "The Handmaid's Tale" presents a complex and multifaceted exploration of motherhood, revealing its transformative power and the ways it can be both oppressed and reclaimed.

In "Mrs. Dalloway" by Virginia Woolf, the image of motherhood is nuanced and reflects the complexities of women's roles in society. Clarissa's thoughts often drift to her past and her relationship with her mother. Her mother represents traditional femininity and societal expectations, creating a contrast between Clarissa's desires and the roles imposed on her. Clarissa's memories of her mother evoke a sense of longing and nostalgia. The absence of her mother, who died when Clarissa was young, influences her feelings of identity and belonging.

Clarissa grapples with her own role as a wife and mother, reflecting societal pressures. Her internal conflicts reveal the struggle between personal fulfillment and societal expectations of motherhood. The character of Septimus Warren Smith's wife, Rezia, highlights another aspect of motherhood, as she navigates her husband's mental health struggles. Her care for him underscores the burdens placed on women, often overshadowing their own needs. The novel touches on themes of mental health, particularly through Septimus, paralleling Clarissa's own existential reflections. The pressure to conform to maternal roles can exacerbate feelings of isolation and anxiety. The interactions between characters suggest a continuum of maternal influence, with Clarissa's experiences shaping her understanding of motherhood and femininity. Overall, "Mrs. Dalloway" presents a complex portrayal of motherhood, intertwining themes of memory, identity, and societal expectations.

These interpretations underscore the depth of the mother image, illustrating its significance in shaping identity and human experience in literature.

While Uzbek literature tends to focus on the traditional, sacrificial role of mothers within the family and society, English literature often explores a broader spectrum of

maternal experiences, emphasizing individual struggles and contemporary challenges. These differences highlight how cultural contexts shape the portrayal of motherhood.

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